

1 FIGURES

2 Figure 1. Native Mexican range for Lilac-crowned Parrot (purple) and Red-crowned Parrot (red)
3 and introduced range for both species (green) in southern California. Data for species ranges
4 were drawn from eBird status and trends data.

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7 Figure 2. Environmental niche divergence between Red-crowned and Lilac-crowned Parrots in
 8 their native and introduced ranges. (a) Plot of divergence in environmental space (E-space) for
 9 the first and second principal component (PC) describing 56% of the total variation. Biological
 10 interpretations of the PC axes are derived from variable loadings in Table S1. Ovals represent the
 11 95% confidence ellipse of the occurrence points (red and purple lines) and the background
 12 points, which reflect the available environmental space in the flying distance of the occurrence
 13 records. (b) Comparing the distributions of inhabited conditions by introduced and native
 14 populations. For each panel, the standard interpretation of the given BioClim variable is the plot
 15 title.

17 Figure 3. Reciprocal species distribution models for the (a) Red-crowned and (b) Lilac-crowned
18 Parrots in their native ranges in Mexico, separately projected onto their introduced range in
19 southern California. Percentages and the total area of suitable habitat quantified by thresholding
20 with the minimum training presence (MTP) are listed for each respective model. Maximum
21 suitability scores did not exceed 0.25 and 0.16 for the Red-crowned and Lilac-crowned Parrots
22 respectively, showing much less suitable habitat in the introduced region.

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25 Figure 4. Observed area of niche unfilling (native range), expansion (introduced range), and
26 stability (overlap) for the (a) Red-crowned and (b) Lilac-crowned Parrots. No niche overlap is
27 observed for either species, dashed lines represent the extent of background environmental
28 variation for each region and the gray shading represents the occurrence densities within the
29 native range.

31 Figure 5. Comparison of niche shifts in various introduced Red-crowned Parrot populations. (a)
 32 Plot of divergence in environmental space for the first and second principal component (PC)
 33 describing 69% of the total variation. Ovals represent the 95% confidence ellipse of the points.
 34 Each green oval represents the breadth of environmental conditions (background) of each
 35 corresponding region shown by line type. (b) Univariate divergence of environmental variables
 36 between each region.

